

Cross-Platform Retrieval Mechanism Comparison

Perplexity, ChatGPT and Gemini on Identical Queries (GEO Lab Experiment E042)

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Abstract

E042 is an exploratory cross-platform observation, not a pre-registered controlled experiment, mapping how Perplexity, ChatGPT and Gemini retrieve in response to the same nine queries (three length tiers across three GEO Lab concept pages), captured in a single same-day session via browser network traces, for 27 data points. Citation outcomes diverged sharply: Perplexity 6/9 (67%), ChatGPT 5/9 (56%), and Gemini 0/9 (0%), revealing three structurally different retrieval architectures. ChatGPT operates a binary pre-retrieval gate that short conceptual queries fail (returning geospatial and training-data content) and that long-form, named-platform, causal queries bypass; it also cites from an entity-graph level rather than from specific page retrieval. Gemini in Flash-fallback mode cited nothing across all nine queries and on one query adopted a competitor's framework framing wholesale. Two queries failed on all three platforms, both attributable to query construction rather than to the site. A robots.txt audit found that no competitor blocks any AI crawler, so competitive displacement is content and rank driven, not infrastructure driven. The results provide a mechanism-level account of the cross-platform citation differences observed across the wider GEO Lab portfolio.

1. Background and motivation

The GEO Lab portfolio establishes *that* AI platforms cite the same pages at very different rates, but none of the prior experiments observes *why* at the retrieval-mechanism level. Browser network-trace capture across the three platforms now makes the mechanism observable: sub-query counts, query-rewrite behaviour, deep-crawl activation, retrieval-set composition, and snippet extraction, on the same queries in the same time window. E042 structures this into a cross-platform mechanism map. It is an exploratory observation with a documented, reproducible protocol, not a controlled experiment with pre-registered falsification criteria.

2. Method

Nine queries were used, three length tiers (2 to 4 words, 6 to 8 words, 10 to 12 words) across three GEO Lab concept pages (*/geo-stack/*, */extractability/*, */retrieval-probability/*), one query per tier per page. This is the same query set used in the E030 length-versus-citation experiment, allowing direct comparison of mechanism data against citation-rate data on a per-query basis. All nine queries were run on all three platforms within a single same-day session, controlling for temporal variance.

Capture was per platform: Perplexity via the */rest/thread* endpoint trace (search query field, retrieval set, navigate events); ChatGPT via the network tab (sub-query fan-out and extracted snippet fields); Gemini via its encoded *batchexecute* calls (sub-query count, outbound search calls, domain presence). Per query, the recorded fields included sub-query count and texts, query-rewrite flag and text, deep-crawl activation, full retrieval-set domains, target-page presence and rank, competitor (ThatWare, Hashmeta) presence and rank, geospatial-namespace noise count, citation outcome, the extracted snippet, and network-trace readability. A robots.txt accessibility audit (research question 7) was run after the session on every domain that appeared in any retrieval set.

3. Results

3.1 Citation outcomes and the determinism matrix

Each cell records whether the target page was cited and whether the correct page was retrieved. Rank is the target page's position in the retrieval set where present.

Perplexity — 6/9 cited (67%)

Page	2-4 word	6-8 word	10-12 word
/geo-stack/	Y rank 5	Y rank 5	N wrong page
/extractability/	Y rank 2	Y rank 6	N absent
/retrieval-probability/	Y rank 1	Y rank 1	N absent

ChatGPT — 5/9 cited (56%)

Page	2-4 word	6-8 word	10-12 word
/geo-stack/	N GIS noise	Y entity graph	Y homepage only
/extractability/	Y rank 2	Y rank 3	N absent
/retrieval-probability/	Y homepage	N absent	N absent

Gemini (Flash fallback) — 0/9 cited (0%)

Page	2-4 word	6-8 word	10-12 word
/geo-stack/	N no grounding	N no grounding	N ThatWare rank 1
/extractability/	N no grounding	N no grounding	N absent
/retrieval-probability/	N GIS misfire	N absent	N absent

3.2 Cross-platform agreement

No query was cited by all three platforms. Four of nine queries were cited by two platforms, three by one platform only, and two by none. The two three-platform failures (the 10 to 12 word extractability and retrieval-probability queries) are query-construction failures, not site failures: in one the word ‘Perplexity’ routed the entire retrieval set to Perplexity-specific SEO content on all three platforms, and in the other a dropped ‘GEO’ context shifted retrieval to general AI and machine-learning literature on all three.

3.3 Per-platform mechanism

Perplexity runs live retrieval-augmented generation with a visible retrieval set. Query rewriting and a visible three-step sub-query decomposition appeared at the 10 to 12 word tier (the first observed fan-out decomposition). Binding patterns were stable, and the competitor pages ThatWare and Hashmeta entered the retrieval set on GEO Stack queries. It was the most reliable citation platform in the set, with the correct page retrieved on four of its six cited queries.

ChatGPT operates a binary pre-retrieval gate. Short conceptual queries do not trigger retrieval and return geospatial or training-data content (the 2 to 4 word GEO Stack query returned 79% geospatial noise with no GEO or AI sources). The gate is bypassed by long-form queries combining a named platform and causal framing. Notably, ChatGPT cites from an entity-graph level rather than specific page retrieval: on the 6 to 8 word GEO Stack query it cited thegeolab.net eight times with 12 of 17 source links pointing to the domain, yet the /geo-stack/ slug itself was absent, the answer being synthesised from eight other slugs. This session recorded the first confirmed ChatGPT citation of thegeolab.net in the portfolio.

Gemini, in Flash-fallback mode, grounds via Google Search but cited nothing across all nine queries; Flash fallback suppresses source cards. Short tiers triggered geospatial misfires (the 2 to 4 word retrieval-probability query produced an answer about geostationary satellites and location-privacy mathematics). On the 10 to 12 word GEO Stack query, grounding activated and Gemini placed ThatWare at rank 1, cited it five times, and adopted ThatWare's five-layer framing wholesale, the most severe competitive displacement in the dataset.

3.4 Namespace collision and infrastructure

Geospatial namespace collision (GEO read as geography) was worst at the 2 to 4 word tier across all platforms, where short queries lack the context to disambiguate. The robots.txt audit found that thegeolab.net, thatware.co and hashmeta.ai all allow PerplexityBot, GPTBot, ClaudeBot and Googlebot. No competitor blocks any AI

crawler, so the competitive displacement observed is content and rank driven, not infrastructure driven.

4. Portfolio implications

- The cross-platform citation-rate differences recorded across the portfolio (for example in E014, E016 and E002) are, at least in part, retrieval-mechanism and retrieval-set-composition differences, not purely page-quality differences.
- Gemini's mention-without-citation behaviour is consistent with a grounding mechanism that, in Flash fallback, does not surface source cards; this bounds how Gemini citation should be measured.
- ChatGPT's entity-graph citation means slug-level retrieval presence is not a precondition for a ChatGPT citation, and measurement keyed only to specific-URL retrieval will undercount it.
- Two of nine failures were query-construction artefacts shared across all platforms, a reminder that query design is itself a measurement variable.

5. Limitations

- Exploratory design. One observation per cell from a single same-day session; no pre-registration and no repeated-measures variance estimate.
- Gemini mode. The Gemini arm ran in Flash fallback, not Pro; the 0/9 citation result is bounded to that mode and may not hold for Gemini Pro.
- Trace readability. Network-trace readability varied by platform (Gemini calls are encoded), so some fields are observed with lower confidence.
- Single time window. Same-day capture controls temporal variance but cannot speak to day-to-day stability of these mechanisms.

6. Data availability

The dataset accompanies this record and is mirrored in the replication package on GitHub (github.com/arturseo-geo/geo-lab-experiments, e042 directory). Files: e042_cross_platform_mechanism_map.csv (27 rows, full per-query mechanism data), e042_robots_txt_audit.csv (per-domain AI-crawler accessibility), e042_competitor_rank_log.csv (competitor ranks per query), and e042_determinism_matrix.md (the citation-outcome matrix). The research note is published at <https://thegeolab.net/e042-cross-platform-retrieval-mechanism-map/>.

Cite as: Ferreira, A. (2026). *Cross-Platform Retrieval Mechanism Comparison: Perplexity, ChatGPT and Gemini on Identical Queries (GEO Lab Experiment E042)*. The GEO Lab working paper. CC BY 4.0.